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Breathing New Life into Nature's Pharmacy: Current Status and Conservation of Medicinal Plants in Sub -Division Jared (Kaghan Valley)

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ABSTRACT

The government of Pakistan has launched a massive afforestation campaign to revive the depleting state of forests of the province for this purpose an ambitious project was initiated known as the "Billion Tree Afforestation Project" or BTAP. The project aims at planning, designing, commencing and implementing "Green Growth Initiative" in the Forestry Sector of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province. A study on the impact of BTAP project on medicinal flora of JARED sub division was conducted. The aim of the study was to assess the impacts of BTAP project on medicinal plants of JARED sub division. The methodology of the study focused on a series of surveys to find out the regeneration status and diversity of medicinal plants inside and outside the BTAP project area (enclosures). The study revealed 11 important medicinal plants which are present both inside and outside enclosures. Further the study reveals that a total of 6779 medicinal plants were present in the survey area inside enclosures and a total of 1328 medicinal plants were present in study area outside the enclosures. Further calculations were done to find out the Relative Cover and Relative frequency of medicinal plants in study area. The results of these calculations show that Relative cover of all medicinal plants inside enclosure area was 68% while outside enclosure area was 34.75%. Similarly, the results from calculations show relative frequency sum as 154 for inside enclosures and 69 for outside of enclosure area. The research has shown massive regeneration and intensity of medicinal flora on the sites upon which BTAP activities were done. The formation of closures specifically has really enhanced growth of medicinal flora, in comparison with open sites the density of medicinal flora in closures is greater. The field data that is collected shows 2-3 times more number of medicinal plants on BTAP sites than elsewhere. Not only are the numbers greater on BTAP sites but also the diversity of medicinal flora on BTAP sites is greater. The study also reveals that through this project a great number of species are being conserved in situ through the formation of enclosures.

Keywords: Afforestation; Billion Tree Afforestation Project (BTAP); Medicinal flora; Biodiversity conservation; Green Growth Initiative; Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Plants have been used in various traditional medicinal systems for the treatment of human ailments. Indigenous cultures' traditional medical knowledge of medicinal plants and their applications is important for community healthcare, medication development, biodiversity preservation, and cultural traditions preservation. The tribal and rural people primarily depend on locally available plants for healthcare and treatment of diseases prevailing in men, women and children. Such health care practices are all culturally, socially and environmentally closure to the masses and were systematically recorded and incorporated in pharmacopeias of many eastern countries like India, China and become the *Materia Medica* of the traditional medicine (Wali et al., 2022).

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In the current landscape of illness treatment, it is critical to identify alternative medical systems for the management of diseases that are constantly evolving, particularly those that may be cured with the use of herbal remedies and do not require lengthy medical interventions. In developing nations, medicinal plants can be a substantial source of revenue for rural populations, particularly when it comes to the sale of material collected in the wild, which accounts for 15% to 30% of lower-class households' overall income. In the Himalayan region, the value of medicinal plants is becoming more widely acknowledged, and especially from the viewpoints of ecology, society, and economy (Negi et al., 2023). Degradation has altered the structural characteristics of the over story in native old-growth forests, endangering the diversity and richness of understory medicinal plant species, despite their importance to rural lives. Numerous studies have documented alterations in the composition of Himalayan forests, with the majority attributing these changes to human activity. For instance, the diversity and quantity of understory species have rapidly declined as a result of forest degradation in the Himalayas. However, it has been noted that in other parts of the world, if degraded forests are permitted to regenerate, there is a higher chance that understory species that had previously vanished will reappear (Dar & Parthasarathy, 2023).

Over 600 medicinal plants are among the approximately 6000 kinds of flowering plants that have been identified and documented in Pakistan thus far. Ethnobotany, which records the covert applications of plants, has grown in importance in modern society. The traditional knowledge on the uses of plants as medicines by the healers and tribal communities is mainly passed on verbally from generation to generation. Recently the new government in KPK has launched a massive afforestation campaigns to revive the depleting state of forests of the province for this purpose an ambitious project was initiated known as the "Billion Tree Afforestation Project" or BTAP (Abbas et al., 2023). The project aims at planning, designing, commencing and implementing "Green Growth Initiative" in the Forestry Sector of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province. The project will thus, support Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Forest Department, as a catalyst, to plan, design, and launch sustainable development in the Forestry Sector (through active involvement of local communities) and promote green jobs. It will accordingly result in enhancement of forest resource base, rehabilitation and improvement of existing forest ecosystems of the province, arresting environmental degradation, livelihood improvement and job creation for rural youth at their door-step. The project objectives are thus positively correlated with the sector objectives both at federal and provincial levels. The portion of the project that encourages the medicinal flora is perhaps the formation of enclosures. The enclosures refer to an area of the forest that is completely closed for any type of activity and a "Nigehbaan" or guard from the local community is hired to protect it. The enclosures serve as a great regeneration spot for ground flora which is mostly grasses and medicinal shrubs or herbs (Mustafa et al., 2023).

Started in 2014 the project is now enhanced into 10BTAP under the Ministry of climate change. According to the data available up till now through this project 203,575 ha area has been planted and 4,509 enclosures have been established. Of course planting a billion trees has its impacts on the overall environment of the area and thus BTAP has impacted the overall environment of KPK. The project went through strict monitoring by third parties and is now a recognized project internationally. This project is now being termed as the 4th biggest initiative of Afforestation and Re-Afforestation of the world and has also met the Bonn challenges and the time uphill now it had been enhanced enough that it is converted into programmed environment under the Ministry of climate change. The research objectives of the study are as follows:

- To assess the impact of BTAP activities on important medicinal plants.
- To explore the diversity of medicinal flora.

The formation of enclosures under BTAP has a direct impact on the occurrence of medicinal plants. The following are the research objectives of the study, i.e.

- I) How has the formation of enclosures under BTAP impacted the number of medicinal plants?
- II) What is the effect of enclosure formation on the regeneration of medicinal plants?
- III) To what extent has the enclosure formation impacted the Relative frequency (RF), Relative cover (RC) and Relative density (RD) of medicinal plants?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The main cause of depletion of medicinal plants from our wild resources and a matter of prime concern is the large scale exploitation of medicinal plants for commercial purposes. To meet the growing industrial demands, extensive collection of medicinal plants is undertaken by those teenaged in the trade. There has been no attempt to augment the availability of these plants through cultivation. This has naturally led to an imbalance in the plant population of certain species. Much of the damage is confined to species that are from high altitude zones, particularly because the regeneration prospects of individual species found at this alleviation are limited by difficult conditions. A considerable amount of work regarding conservation of medicinal plants has been done in the past, a lot more is going on in different regions of the world but a more comprehensive approach is still needed.

2.1. Conservation as Tradition

In some regions of the world, local people have made the preservation of natural resources a part of their traditions. The tribal people of China's Gwangxi Karst Region, the Mayamba District of Sierra Leone, and Meghalaya in Northeast India. They all have a tradition of environmental conservation base on various religious beliefs, which have passed from one generation to another. Based on these beliefs certain patches of forests on hills and mountains are designated as sacred grooves or holly hills under customary laws and are well protected from any product extraction by the community. Such forests are very rich in biological diversity and harbor many endangered plant species including rare herbs and medicinal plants (Bargali et al., 2023).

2.2. Conservation of Traditional Knowledge and Ethnobotanical Study

Documentation of traditional knowledge prevailing in different areas of the world will lead towards its conservation. A considerable work is going on in several parts the world e.g. there is a study which documents the abundance, distribution and knowledge of medicinal plant species in a Ransadayak village and adjoining forest in west Kalimantan, Indonesia. Over 250 medicinal plant species from 165 genera and 75 families were utilized by the local healer (Caniago & Stephen, 1998). 81 herbal drug species in 51 families and 77 genera have been documented from Nepal (Manandhar, 1995). Little is known about traditional knowledge and practices developed by the transhumance society on available plants, animal resources, medical herbs and other technologies of high altitude Himalayas, where resources are scarce. Traditional knowledge of some important herbs in their society, traditional cattle breeding achievements, and the traditional handicrafts of high altitude Himalayan is documented and the immediate need for value addition in these sectors in order to save them from extinction and to add to the income of the people has been suggested (Farooquee & Nautiyal, 1999). An inventory of wild edible plants of Indian Himalaya used by local communities has been formulated. Over 675 wild plant species, representing 384 genera and 149 families, are edible (Samant & Dhar, 1997). The past and present status of natural tropical thorn forest in Punjab have been described and *Salvadoraoleoides* has been given special attention because of its great ecological and ethnobotanical importance. The traditional medical uses of about 37 medicinal plants found in Makran were described (Leporatti & Lattanzi, 1994). Similarly, traditional knowledge on 114 plant species was gathered from a diverse population that was nurtured in Baluchistan. Plant utilization studies of Northeastern Baluchistan has also been conducted (Shinwari & Malik, 1989). An initial set of ethnobotanical data was collected from six Baluchistan areas. Additionally, ethnobotanical data pertaining to Baluchistan's Kharan district has been recorded.

In the recent years more efforts have been made to document the traditional knowledge particularly found in Himalayas. In this regard traditional utilization of 160 plants have been described, collecting the knowledge from Margalla Hills National Park Islamabad. About 58 species of medicinal plants have been preliminarily listed from Ayubia National Park Galiyat (Shah, 2001). Indigenous knowledge of about 25 medicinal plants from Kahuta Rawalpindi district have been reported (Qureshi & Khan, 2001). Similarly, traditional uses of about 77 species have been reported from Shogran Valley Mansehra (Matin et al., 2001). There is additional documentation of the traditional use of roughly 69 medicinal plants that can be found in Azad Kashmir's Machiara National Park. There is documented indigenous knowledge of over 85 medicinal plants in Northern Chitral. It has also been investigated how locals in the Khairpur district, the Nara desert, and Cholistan use medicinal plants.

The ethno botanical data on various medicinal uses of some plants of Tehsil Kharian, District Gujrat, and Punjab was documented by using a questionnaires and open ended interviews of local people of study area. A total of 50 plant species belonging to 32 families were identified and it was noticed that the indigenous people of the study area use plants in different ways in their daily life such as medicines, fuel, shelter, forage/fodder, etc. Two Families were found abundant among all the families, i.e. Poaceae and Asteraceae, having 5 and 4 species under ethnobotanical use, respectively (Ajaib et al., 2014). Traditionally, plants have been used as a source of medicine in India by indigenous people inhabiting various terrains for the control of different ailments afflicting human. An ethno botanical survey was undertaken in Nabarangpur District, Odisha, India. The plants and their traditional use are part of the natural and cultural heritage of the region. Finally, the data were assessed to which extent plants are vulnerable due to collection and habitat destruction. Data were collected through field assessments from traditional healers and locals by means of personal interviews and semi-structured questionnaires. A total of 69 plant species belonging to 43 families are reported during the study. The major life forms were herbs, trees, shrubs, climbers, small tree and creeper. Several medicinal plants recognized for the treatment of various diseases were collected. This study reveals that medicinal plants still play a vital role in the primary healthcare of this local community. Traditional medicines also have the potential to form the basis of pharmaceutical drugs for the treatment of a range of diseases (Dhal et al., 2014). The present research work was designed to gather indigenous knowledge of local people especially medicinal healers (Hakims) about traditional and medicinal uses of plants. Present study was confined to interview people of remote villages of tehsil Shakargarh, district Narowal, Pakistan from September 2003- August 2004. Indigenous knowledge was collected by interviewing people of different age groups between 40 to 80 years. Frequent field trips were arranged

to record local information. A total of 102 species belonging to 93 genera and 62 families were recorded as being used by local inhabitants for various purposes such as fuel, furniture, fodder, making baskets and mats, brushing teeth, medicinal, vegetables and edible fruits (Sardar & Zaheer-Ud-Din, 2009). This paper reflects the empirical findings of an ethno botanical survey which was undertaken in Patriate (New Murree) of district Rawalpindi in Pakistan. Documenting indigenous knowledge of plants, especially those used for medical, veterinary, fruit, vegetable, fodder, fuel, etc., was one of the study's goals.

2.3. Conservation Criteria

There have been several attempts to construct systems for setting priorities for conservation on a national or regional level (Sparrowe & Wight, 1975; Millsap et al., 1990; Avery et al., 1995; Catling & Porebski, 1998). A variety of different criteria used in different combinations and systems have been suggested. However, red lists and red data books of IUCN have been used for over 30 years to draw attention to threatened species the world over. The IUCN categories of threat are now accepted and used by varied group of people involved in conservation of biodiversity.

According to the Red data book of ICUN (1970), the status of commercially important indigenous species can be determined using the following four parameters;

- I. Availability
- II. Collection
- III. Part used
- IV. Growth

Using these parameters, the relative usefulness of medicinal plants can be classified into Endangered, Vulnerable, Rare, Infrequent, and Dominant. In 1994, IUCN adopted new criteria to assess the risks of extinction at the global scale, and it became apparent that they could produce misleading results when applied at the regional or national level. Revised criteria are more objective, numerical and scientific as well as having greater applicability across taxon groups and are meant to be used for all organisms except micro-organisms. The considerations for the selection are as follows:

- a) Global recognition of the species;
- b) Rapid destruction of its limited habitat;
- c) Extensive haunting pressure for food and trade;
- d) Representation of each major group;
- e) Economic importance of the species; and
- f) Distribution of the species.

Revised categories (in 2002) are 'Extinct', 'Critically endangered', 'extinct in the wild', 'Endangered', 'vulnerable', 'Low risk', 'Data deficient' and 'Not evaluated'. Another approach for prioritization of medicinal plants for conservation was developed after analyzing the available information on various aspects of medicinal plants of the Indian Himalayan region. Prioritization was based on three indices:

- 1) Use value index (UVI) indicates threats imposed by users.
- 2) Sensitivity index (SI) reflects conservation concerns of biologists and
- 3) Importance value index (IVI) is the cumulative value of (1) and (2) to prevent biased approach.

Twenty top ranking medicinal plants are identified for conservation in each life form (Dhar et al., 2000).

2.4. Conservation Status of Medicinal Plants

Indiscriminate and non-systematic collection of medicinal plants in various parts of the world has led to severe pressure on the availability of medicinal plant, many of which are now rare, threatened or endangered. What is the conservation status of medicinal plants and how many species of medicinal plants are threatened today? No one knows. "Knowing what species are traded commercially is the foundation for identifying threatened plants". According to recent figures from the IUCN threatened plants database (Walter & Gillet, 1998) approximately 32,000 species of plants are threatened with extinction. This figure represents approx. 13% of the estimated 250,000 species of higher plants and bryophytes on earth, but does not take into account the many species whose status has not yet been assessed. A widely quoted estimate by (Farnsworth & Soejarto, 1991) based on records in the NAPRALERT database, is that 28% of plants have been used in ethno medicine. Putting these estimates together (28% of 13% of 250,000 plant species) allows the conclusion that roughly 9,000 species of medicinal plants are threatened worldwide. Naturally, this number does not include any species whose applications are currently unknown or poorly understood.

About 15% i.e., 4000-5000 out of total 30,000 vascular plants in China is estimated to be rare and endangered. Without assigning IUCN threat categories, besides Bryoniaceticass (almost extinct) 13 taxa have been assessed as 'endangered' and 9 other

taxa are regarded as over collected or otherwise threatened from Egypt. Six species (viz. *Aconitum heterophyllum*, *Podophyllum hexandrum*, *Nardostachys jatamansi*, *Picrorhiza kurroa*, *Swertia chirayita*, and *Bergenia ciliata*) were considered as test cases for successful conservation for a large number of species in Sikkim that are claimed to have therapeutic value and whose survival in the wild is being threatened (Rai et al., 2000).

2.5. Community Based Conservation

On the social side, local community benefits related to medicinal plants are a matter of serious neglect. Medicinal plants are one biological resource next to food crops whose earliest and most knowledgeable custodians are local and indigenous communities. Yet local communities do not get a fair share of the benefits generated from trade, processing or production. They are also not sufficiently involved by Government in conservation programs. They are not even adequately acknowledged by their many innovations and practical knowledge about the uses of plants.

Ecologically fragile landscapes of the Himalaya, particularly rain forest areas, have been experiencing increased degradation of land and water, and loss of biodiversity. Based on the primary information, and constant interaction between the scientists and farmers, an eco-friendly alternative model for sustainable and optimal utilization of land has been developed and demonstrated. The people's participation was considered an essential tool for successful implementation of the action plan. As a result, the villagers themselves conducted the fieldwork and following actions under the encouragement and direction of specialists.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Selection of Sampling Fraction: The purpose of our study was to compare the effect of enclosure formation on the occurrence of important medicinal plants, for achieving this objective 1% sampling intensity was used inside the enclosures and same number of plots were taken outside enclosures irrespective of the fact that area outside enclosures is not equal to the area inside. This was done for comparison purpose as sampling 1% of total outside area was not feasible. So for sound comparison same numbers of plots were sampled inside and outside. The study was carried out in both phases of BTAP intervention sites. The data for enclosures and outside of enclosures was collected separately. The data was collected through multi-stage random sampling procedure in which 4 out of 38 enclosures were selected at 10% sampling intensity. To ensure randomization these enclosures were selected through balloting. And further 1% area was surveyed out of total area of enclosures. This 1% area was divided into 38 plots of 66*66 feet i.e., 1/10th of an acre and distributed throughout the whole enclosure area by systemized sampling. First an approximate center of the enclosure area was located and the sample plots were taken after every 330 steps in all four directions.

3.2. Season of Data Collection: The data was collected in the month of September that is the period of late Monsoon. This season shows the maximum availability of medicinal plants and thus the data collected helps formulate a clear picture of the impact of enclosure formation.

3.3. Method of Survey: In each enclosure an imaginary center was located and sample plots were taken in all the four directions. The size of sample plot was 66*66', i.e. 1/10 of an acre. For randomization, the plots were taken after every 330 steps approximately. The distance between the two sample plots were measured with the help of a pedometer. In all 38 sample plots will be studied in the four compartments covering 376.82-acre actual area of the plots. The same number of plots i.e., 38 will be surveyed outside the enclosure area for comparison of data. Number of every medicinal plant will be recorded in the sample plot and their distribution frequencies will be calculated.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The use of medicinal plants in the study area was enormous and the dependence of local community on medicinal herbs for their ailments is indispensable. Medicinal plants are being used for treatment of both humans and their livestock. Some species are available in huge numbers and so their use is common and cheap for the local communities. The selection of the medicinal plant species to be surveyed was done in accordance with the available literature and through consulting local working plans. The results gathered through this study show huge difference in the regeneration and number of medicinal plants between enclosures and outside areas. The total number of medicinal plants found inside the enclosures is 6779 and the total number of medicinal plants found outside of enclosure area is 1328. This data is shown below compartment wise in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Medicinal Plant Diversity Inside vs. Outside Sampling Units

Source: Field Survey.

Figure 1 shows a significant difference in the total number of medicinal plants in the sample plots present inside and outside enclosures. The difference is not limited to a specific compartment or enclosure but is reflected in whole of sampling units or plots. If we further elaborate on the data collected in the form of frequency per species for all the compartments here also a huge difference is observed between enclosure area and outside area. This is shown with the help of following chart in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Comparison of Medicinal Plant Species Frequency inside and outside Enclosures

Source: Field Survey.

Figure 2 clearly shows a significant change in the frequency per species in the enclosure area and outside area. Total average frequency of all medicinal plant species inside enclosures is 14, whereas total average frequency of all medicinal plant species outside enclosures is 6.27. The data collected per compartment for medicinal plant species in term of cover percentage is another base of comparison between the presence of medicinal plant species inside and outside enclosures. The total cover of said medicinal plant species per compartment is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Contrasting Medicinal Plant Cover Inside and Outside Enclosures

Source: Field Survey.

Figure 3 shows the difference between cover of medicinal plants inside and outside enclosures. The average cover inside enclosures is 68 and outside enclosure is 34.75. The following data in Table 1 and Table 2 shows the presence of medicinal plant species in terms of Relative Density (RD), Relative Cover (RC) and Relative frequency (RF) both inside and outside enclosures.

Table 1: Medicinal Plant Species Presence inside Enclosures

Species	Relative Frequency (%)	Relative Cover (%)	Relative Density (%)
Artemisia fragrans (Chao)	4.55	6.6	2.91
Berberis lyceum Royle (Sumbal)	11.04	9.2	6.37
Bergenia ciliate (Butpewah)	9.74	11.4	6.28
Bistorta amplexaule (Masloon)	22.73	14.0	25.03
Geranium wallachianum (Ratanjok)	17.53	10.7	22.97
Paeonia emodi (Mamekh)	7.79	5.9	10.96
Rumex nepalensis (Hola)	4.55	7.7	8.51
Swertia chiraita (Charata)	0.65	5.5	0.46
Valeriana wallichii (Mushkbala)	14.29	8.5	11.33
Viburnum continifolium (Guch)	5.19	8.8	4.66
Zanthoxylum armatum (Timar)	1.95	11.8	0.52

Table 2 shows the Relative Frequency percentage data outside closures and it is observed that Bistorta amplexicaulis (Masloon) has the highest relative frequency of 34.78% whereas both Viburnum continifolium (Guch) and Zanthoxylum armatum (Timar) have lowest relative frequency percentage of 0%.

Table 2: Medicinal Plant Species Presence outside Enclosures

Species	Relative Frequency (%)	Relative Cover (%)	Relative Density (%)
Artemisia fragrans (Chao)	2.90	14.39	2.33
Berberis lyceum Royle (Sumbal)	13.04	17.27	5.80
Bergenia ciliate (Butpewah)	5.80	10.07	9.11
Bistorta amplexaule (Masloon)	34.78	25.90	43.00
Geranium wallachianum (Ratanjok)	17.39	15.11	16.72
Paeonia emodi (Mamekh)	2.90	6.47	4.52
Rumex nepalensis (Hola)	2.90	2.16	2.48

Species	Relative Frequency (%)	Relative Cover (%)	Relative Density (%)
Swertia chiraita (Charata)	7.25	5.04	7.15
Valeriana wallichii(Mushkbala)	13.04	3.60	8.89
Viburnum continifolium(Guch)	0	0	0
Zanthoxylum armatum(Timar)	0	0	0

To further strengthen the claim of our results a paired-samples t-test was conducted to compare the regeneration of medicinal plants inside and outside enclosures and analyze the significance of our results (see, Table 3).

Table 3: Paired-Samples t-Test

Species	Inside	Outside	A-B	(A-B) ²
Masloon	1697	571	1126	1267876
Ratanjok	1557	222	1335	1782225
Pat pay	426	121	305	93025
Mamekh	743	60	683	466489
Sumbal	432	77	355	126025
Charata	31	95	-64	4096
Chahu	197	31	166	27556
Bakai	577	33	544	295936
Mushkbala	768	118	650	422500
Timbar	35	0	35	1225
Guch	316	0	316	99856
			$\sum d = 5451$	$\sum d = 4586809$

During data collection from JARED forest sub division it was observed that the dependence of local people on the medicinal plants for various ailments was enormous in their day to day activities. From the study area the following medicinal plant species were found commonly and their use was common among the general population (see, Table 4).

Table 4: Medicinal Plants and Their Uses

Medicinal Plant	Vernacular Names	Family	Parts Used	Medicinal Use
1) Berberis lyceum Royle	Sumbal, Kashmal, Zirishk, Berberry	Berberidaceae	Dried roots	Relief of intestinal colic, cooling agent, treatment of throat pains, mouth diseases, and fever.
2) Bergeniaciliata (Haw.) Sternb.	Butpehwa/Zakh-mi-Hiyat	Saxifragaceae	Rhizomes	Healing wounds, treatment of colon cancer, muscular pains, teething, and as a tonic.
3) Bistortaamplexicaule (D. Don)	Masloon, Bistort	Polygonaceae	Leaves, rhizome, root	Joint pain relief, cough treatment, general body tonic, and pneumonia remedy.
4) Geranium wallachianum (D. Don ex Sweet)	Ratanjot, Laljhari	Geraniaceae	Dried rhizomes	Tonic for backache, and as a tonic for various ailments.
5) Paeoniaemodi Wall	Mamekh, Udsalib,	Paeoniaceae	Tuberous roots	Treatment for

Medicinal Plant	Vernacular Names	Family	Parts Used	Medicinal Use
ex Royle	Paeony Rose			rheumatism, backache, and other pains.
6) Zanthoxylumarmatum D.C.	Timar, Tejbal, Prickly ash	Rutaceae	Bark, Fruit	Improve digestion, cure toothache, and used as a toothbrush.
7) Artemisia fragrans L.	Chao	Asteraceae	Leaves	Anthelmintic, treatment for wounds, earache, toothache, and asthma.
8) Swertiachiraita	Charata	Gentianaceae	Whole plant	Treatment against fever and malaria.
9) Valerianawallichii	Mushkbala	Valerianaceae	Roots	Sedative, used in obesity, skin diseases, epilepsy, and snake poisoning.
10) Viburnum continifolium	Guch	Adoxaceae	Whole plant	Anthelmintic, antibacterial, antibiotic, antiviral, and laxative.
11) Rumexnepalensis	Hola	Polygonaceae	Whole Plant	Purgative root, treatment for dislocated bones, swollen gums, colic, headaches, and body pain relief.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study shows various aspects of the impacts of BTAP on the medicinal flora of JARED forest sub-division. The field data collected shows significant variation in the occurrence of medicinal plants inside and outside enclosures. After detailed study it was concluded that enclosure formation caused a major variation in the total number of medicinal plants. The results show that total number of 6779 plants were present inside enclosures as compared to 1328 number of plants present outside enclosures. Further the frequency per species present inside and outside enclosure shows a significant difference. As shown by the results the total average frequency of all medicinal plant species inside enclosures is 14, whereas total average frequency of all medicinal plant species outside enclosure is 6.27. Field data further suggests the change in the occurrence of medicinal plants species affected by enclosure formation as shown by the average cover which is 68 inside and 34.75 outside. The present study emphasizes on the conservation of medicinally important species through BTAP interventions. There is need to look forward for the preservation of this natural wealth.

Recommendations

The following are the study's recommendations, i.e.,

1. Thorough survey of medicinal plants is needed to be carried out to update the inventory of existing medicinal plant resources in different regions of Kaghan Valley.
2. There is need for long term conservation strategy to truly preserve the important medicinal plants in their natural habitat through 10BTAP.
3. More conservation enclosures should be established through this project in the area.
4. Establishment of nursery of medicinal plants for the supply of quality seed and planting stock to meet excessive demand of medicinal plants.
5. The need of research and education in this field is a pre-requisite for the efficient utilization of the meager resource.
6. Kaghan Valley can be converted into the medicinal valley due to its high potential of medicinal flora present which can be maintained through proper protection and management of these species.
7. The concept of more participatory activities should be implemented to aware the local communities about the importance of medicinal plants and its economic value.
8. Eco-Tourism practices should be more enhanced to provide suitable and sustainable environment to the medicinal flora.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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